

Environmental approach of an enhanced geothermal system for energy efficient building retrofitting in a decentralized context

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ABSTRACT

The life cycle assessment (LCA) is a methodology for assessing environmental impacts associated with the stages of the life cycle (LC) of a product, process, or service. This paper compares the results of the entire LCA (cradle-to-grave analysis) of a hybrid heating geothermal system that includes a novel hybrid heat pump 8kW and set of heating components integrated with the novel ground source heat pump (GSHP) concept which was installed in a building located in the Aran Islands (Ireland) within the framework of the H2020 GEOFIT project against the heating system, that existed before the retrofitting. The building selected for the demonstration had in its original version a 21kW diesel boiler (Firebird model S/90) used for heating and an emission system based on 9 radiators with individual on / off control located in different rooms, as well as a coal stove in the living room.

To determine the heat energy of the building before and after the retrofitting, simulations of the heat energy were carried out with the IDA Indoor Climate and Energy 4.8 simulation software, and the SimaPro v.9.1 program was used to calculate the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The results show that a new heating system (after GEOFIT) is better alternative than conventional one (before GEOFIT), mainly in terms of generating more heat with less heating energy consumption during the operation stage.

The new system can reduce annual operational emissions by more than 53% in comparison to the reference one.

1. INTRODUCTION

Buildings generate about 39% of annual global CO₂ emissions, of those total emissions, building operations are responsible for 28%, while building materials and construction are responsible for 11% (UNEP, 2019). This data comes before COVID-19 which caused a 10% decrease, although the decrease appears to be temporary as emissions will pick up again as economic activity increases (UNEP, 2021). The European Union's Green Deal requires participants to reduce at least 40% GHG emissions compared to that of 1990 levels to achieve at least 32% share for renewable energy and to improve the energy efficiency at least by 32.5%. In this context, Ireland's National Energy and Climate Plan to 2020 (NECP) commits Ireland to an average annual reduction of GHG emissions by 7% annually in 2021-2030 (a reduction of 51% over a decade) and to achieve net zero emissions by 2050 (SEAI, 2021).

The main source of heating in Ireland was coal and peat, which dominated until the 1950s, in the 1960s crude oil and town gas gained popularity, and from the mid-1970s to the end of the 1980s, solid fuel returned, and crude oil and natural gas has found most of the consumers in the last 25 years. Since 2008, building codes in Ireland require new homes to be equipped with some form of renewable energy source (RES) (Ireland 2050).

One of the RES can be geothermal energy, that includes energy obtained from the inside of the Earth, whether in the form of electricity or heat. This source of energy looks to be an excellent alternative to reducing GHG emissions from heating and cooling buildings with fossil fuels, and thanks to its constant supply of concentrated energy, it can support the transition towards a low-carbon economy. In this context geothermal energy can play a crucial role in Ireland as well as whole European energy market.

The study assesses the GEOFIT's enhanced geothermal system with a novel heat pump for heating a building in a climate dominated by heat demand and underline the benefits which has bring its adoption from the point of view of environmental protection. This new technological solution is in line with the expectations of the energy market, which is predicted that heat pumps will meet 20% of buildings' thermal energy needs by 2030, compared to 5% in 2019 (IEA, 2021).

2. LCA METHODOLOGY

The LCA is a standardized methodology to assess the environmental impacts of a system through its LC. The ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006 standards provide the framework for performing an LCA, which consist of four phases.

The first phase is to define the goal and scope of the assessment, its objectives, functional unit (FU), and system boundaries. The scope of the study determines which processes should be included in the inventory phase of the assessment. In the second phase, the life cycle inventory (LCI) includes information on all the inputs and outputs associated with a product or service, i.e., material and energy requirements, as well as emissions and waste. The third phase is the impact assessment, where the potential contribution of each substance to predefined environmental impact categories is calculated. Once the impact has been calculated, the fourth and final step of the assessment is the interpretation, where the results of the calculations are summarized and discussed.

The LCA analysis of this study was performed in accordance with European ISO standards and ILCD Handbook developed by the Joint Research Center of the European Commission. Furthermore, LCA has as well based in the "Life Cycle Phases of Energy Systems" reported in PCR UN CPC 171 and 173 *Electricity, steam and hot/cold water generation and distribution* and EN 15804 (IEA, 2016). Software SimaPro v9.1 was used to calculate the environmental indicators.

2.1 Goal and Scope

The main goal and scope of this LCA study was to determine the environmental impacts generated by the construction, operation, maintenance, and end of life (LCA) of improved geothermal technologies which were developed within the framework of the GEOFIT project and comparing them with the energy sources used so far.

In this context, this study focuses on the system-wide analysis of a hybrid geothermal system installed in the Aran Islands (Ireland), which presents a heating solution for a typical single-family house. Additionally, a comparative analysis was carried out with the heating system that was before the retrofitting (baseline scenario), which used only conventional heating methods, such as coal and diesel.

In terms of operational energy, the performance of the heating systems before and after the retrofit was compared using indoor climate simulations via energy modelling software IDA-ICE 4.8 (Indoor Climate and Energy performance simulation program).

Functional unit

In order to compare both situations (before and after GEOFIT), two FU were selected to describe results and conclusions:

1. FU: defined as the annual heating energy consumption to maintain a comfortable indoor building temperature of 20-21° C in a house in the Aran Islands (Ireland).
2. FU: defined as 1 kWh of heating energy generated and distributed to the residential building in the Aran Islands (Ireland)

System boundaries

According to the PCR UN CPC 171 and 173 report, the system under investigation is divided into three modules: upstream, core and downstream. For this analysis above document, EN 15804 and the model proposed by Maria Laura Parisi et al. (2020) have been adapted for the Aran building purposes and the cradle-to-grave system boundaries including the following phases outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: Stages of the LCA for the Aran heating systems

Upstream Module (Secondary data)		Core Module (Primary data)					
Production		Construction		Operation & Maintenance		End of Life	
Raw materials	Energy	Heating system components	Energy used for installation	Operational energy use /heating generation	Replacement of materials	Disposal	Recycling

The upstream module includes the production processes for raw materials and energy consumed by the core module, which is residential building on the Aran Islands. Secondary data were collected from the Ecoinvent 3.6 LCA database.

The core module is represented by the system construction, operation, maintenance, and end of life phases of a thermal energy conversion system. The sources of primary data normally come from producers and operators of processes, systems or they are measured and/or collected in situ of the core module. For the purpose of this study the operational energy was simulated with the IDA-ICE software. IDA ICE is a building energy simulation software. It is a whole-year

detailed and dynamic multi-zone simulation application for study of indoor climate as well as the energy performance of the entire building.

2.2 Life cycle Inventory

Case study

The single-family house under study (Figure 1) is located on the Aran Islands off the western coast of Ireland. The climate in the area is of northern temperate type. The building was originally constructed in 1922 on limestone soil, and its total area is 117 m².

Figure 1: Case study residential building in the Aran Islands (Ireland)

The main changes under the heat energy retrofitting of the studied building concerned the following challenges:

- Improve the thermal properties of the building external walls through thermal insulation.
- Improve heat emission through the installation of an underfloor heating system
- Install an 8kW heat pump and distributing system that is suitable for geothermal applications
- Install a geothermal heat exchanger

Heating of the Aran building is required for six to seven months. The average temperature to be maintained during the heating season is around 20-21°C. Given that Aran has a temperate climate in the north, there is no need for cooling in summer.

To evaluate the operational energy use in the building's heating system, it is modelled in IDA-ICE. The model is validated comparing the simulation results to measured data of heating energy use and indoor air temperature, using locally measured weather data as a boundary condition. The comparison between measured and simulated indoor temperatures is presented in Figure 2. The measured temperature varies more than the simulated one due to imperfect control of the heating system and inconsistencies in e.g. the occupancy and internal loads. However, the overall match between the simulated and measured temperatures is good, with the coefficient of variation of the root mean square error CV(RMSE) being 7.1%. According to ASHRAE guideline 14-2002, an hourly

simulation model can be considered valid if the CV(RMSE) < 30%.

Figure 2: Model validation comparing the measured and simulated indoor temperatures

Before GEOFIT, the building used a diesel boiler (21 kW) to produce heat for a conventional radiator system. After the geothermal retrofit, the building is served by a hybrid heating system, where a floor heating system supplied by geothermal energy covers the base heating load, while the boiler and radiators are conserved to help cover peak loads. Both systems are modelled using the IWEC2 30-year average weather data to compare the systems' energy use before and after retrofit. Most significant parameters of the modelled building and the heating systems are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters used for the simulated building model

Parameter	Value	Unit
Heated area	94	m ²
Walls U-value	0.9-1.3	W/m ² K
Windows U-value	2.9	W/m ² K
Ceiling U-value	1.4	W/m ² K
Floor U-value	3.5	W/m ² K
Infiltration	3	l/m ² s
Internal gains	13	W/m ²
Indoor temperature setpoint	20	°C
Radiator supply temperature	55-70	°C
Floor heating supply temperature	35	°C
Occupants	4	-

The annual heating results of the Aran building, simulated with the software IDA Indoor Climate and Energy 4.8 are presented in Table 3. The results before GEOFIT are based on measured coal and diesel consumptions, which were used to validate the simulation model. The model was then simulated using the same boundary conditions alongside the hybrid heating system to estimate the heating energy use after GEOFIT. The listed electricity use refers to the electricity used by the ground source heat pump, whereas the geothermal heat refers to heating energy produced by the heat pump. For simulation purposes, the design outdoor temperature for heating is 1.2 °C according to the Irish Meteorological Service. (Met Éireann, n.d.), and the underfloor heating installed as part of the retrofitting takes up 94 m² of surface.

Table 3: Annual heating energy consumption results for Aran case building obtained via IDA-ICE simulation

	Before GEOFIT (kWh/Year)	After GEOFIT (kWh/Year)
<i>Electricity grid mix</i>	-	7,893.98
<i>Coal</i>	16,357.13	-
<i>Diesel</i>	8,177.34	3,196.47
<i>Geothermal</i>	-	23,681.95
TOTAL input	24,534.47	11,090.45
TOTAL output	24,534.47	26,878.42

As can be seen from the table above, the GEOFIT hybrid heating system significantly improves the building's efficiency through a visible reduction of more than 54% of heating energy consumption.

Life cycle inventory (LCI) with characteristics of two heating systems and their components considered in this study are summarised in the Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4: Main annual data and characteristics of the thermal heating components before GEOFIT

<i>LC phases</i>	<i>Components</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Lifespan</i>	<i>Raw materials / Energy</i>	<i>Amount</i>	<i>Source</i>
Construction	Diesel boiler 21 kW	1	25 years	Oil boiler 10 kW	2.1 units	Ecoinvent 3.6
	Coal stove	1	-	-	-	-
Operation	Storage electric heater 1.5 kW (radiator)	9	15 years	TEC plastic (PA6)	0.1 kg	Viegand Maagøe, 2019
				Cast iron	30 kg	
				Copper	0.075 kg	
				Aluminum	0.3 kg	
				Electronics (PCBs)	0.1 kg	
				Coating (Silicone)	0.1 kg	
				Electricity (manufacturing)	28.83 kWh	
Operation	Coal stove	1	Annually	Coal	16,357.13 kWh	IDA-ICE simulation
	Diesel boiler 21 kW (DHW)	1	Annually	Diesel	8,177.34 kWh	IDA-ICE simulation
Maintenance	Diesel boiler 21 kW	1	Annually	Oil boiler 10 kW	0.04 units	
	Storage electric heater 1.5 kW (radiator)	1	Annually	Storage electric heater 1.5 kW	0.60 units	
End of life	Diesel boiler 21 kW	1		Recycling 100%	1 units	
	Storage electric heater 1.5 kW (radiator)	9		Metals recycling 100%	-30.38 kg	(EPA, 2021):
				Electronics recycling 100%	-0,1 kg	
				Recycling Plastics 85%	-0.17 kg	(EPA, 2021):
		Landfill Plastic, Silicone	0.03 kg	(EPA, 2021):		

Table 5: Main annual data and characteristics of the thermal heating components after GEOFIT

<i>LC phases</i>	<i>Components</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Lifespan</i>	<i>Raw materials / Energy</i>	<i>Amount</i>	<i>Source</i>
Construction	Borehole heat exchanger 138 m depth, 130 mm of diameter	1	50 years	Mortar (Fischer GeoSolid® 240HS)	30 kg	Provided by GEOFIT, Ecoinvent 3.6
				Water	9400 kg	
				Diesel	879 kWh	
Construction	Borehole pipes PE100 PN16 SDR11	1	50 years	HDPE	166 kg	Provided by GEOFIT, Ecoinvent 3.6
	Heat pump 8 kW (210 kg)	1	20 years	Copper	36.09 kg	
Polyvinylchloride				1.64 kg		
Elastomer, tube insulation				16.41 kg		
Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled				32.81 kg		
Stainless steel				123.05 kg		
refrigerant R410A	1.72 kg					

				Lubricating oil (Polyolester oil)	2.79 kg	
				Electricity, mix grid	112 kWh	
				Heat, district or industrial, natural gas	295 kWh	
	Buffer tank 200 l (65 kg)	1	15 years	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled	65 kg	
	Floor Heating with PE-Xa 9.9 x 1.1 mm pipe	1	50 years	HDPE	35.7 kg	Provided by GEOFIT
EPS				56.2 kg		
electronic component				5 kg		
Mortar				1684.8 kg		
	External Thermal Insulation	1	30 years	EPS, Graphite	162 kg	Provided by GEOFIT
				Rockwool	1771.2 kg	
Operation	Heat pump 8 kW	1	Annually	Electricity grid mix	7,893.98 kWh	IDA-ICE simulation
	Diesel boiler	1	Annually	Diesel	3,196.47 kWh	IDA-ICE simulation
Maintenance	Borehole heat	1	Annually	Borehole heat	0.02 units	
	Heat pump 8 kW	1	Annually	Heat pump 8 kW	0.05 units	
			Annually	Refrigerant R410A (from the initial 6%)	0.10 kg	(Greening & Azapagic, 2012)
	Buffer tank 200 l	1	Annually	Buffer tank 200 l	0.02 units	
	Floor Heating	1	Annually	Floor Heating	0.02 units	
	External Thermal Insulation	1	Annually	External Thermal Insulation	0.033 unit	
End of life	Heat pump 8 kW			Recycling 100%	-210 kg	
	Buffer tank 200 l	1		Recycling 100%	-65 kg	
	Borehole heat, Floor heating, External thermal insulation, Borehole heat	1		Recycling Plastics 85%	-1,862.4 kg	(EPA, 2021):
				Landfill Plastics 15%	328.7 kg	(EPA, 2021):
				Recycling mortar 23%	-394.5 kg	(EPA, 2021):
				Landfill mortar 77%	1,320.3 kg	(EPA, 2021):
		Electronics recycling 100%	5 kg			

Lifespan

The lifespan of thermal energy systems has a significant impact on environmental performance, mainly in the maintenance LC stage where the replacement of materials at the end of their useful life is considered. Table 4 and Table 5 show a lifespan of studied components, which belong to the two studied heating systems.

Impact assessment method

The environmental impact of LCA was considered the GHG emission, which was calculated using the software SimaPro v9.1 and the Ecoinvent v3 database.

The method which was selected for environmental impact calculation is the IPCC 2013 which was used to evaluate 100-years global warming potential (GWP 100a) of different emissions. This method is based on data published by the Intergovernmental Panel on

Climate Change, and expresses the emissions of GHG generated, in kilograms of CO₂ equivalent, over a time horizon of 100 years.

2.2 Results and discussion

The environmental impact related to the entire LCA (cradle-to-grave) of the two studied scenarios: system before GEOFIT (reference) and system after GEOFIT were assessed using the GWP 100a emission indicator. The details of this study are presented below.

GHG emissions

The results of the LCA analysis of the environmental impact of GHG emissions on an annual basis are presented in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Annual impact of GHG emission performance at each LC stage

As illustrated in Figure 3, in terms of GHG emission, the post-GEOFIT building (green bars) performs better than the pre-retrofitting building (grey bars) in total comparison. The new system enables a reduction of approximately 1058 kg CO₂ eq.. The main contribution to GHG emissions comes from the construction and operation stage. In the construction phase, GHG emissions are about 77% (5414 kg CO₂ eq.) higher to the detriment of the new system. This is mainly due to the comprehensive retrofitting of the building as part of the GEOFIT project, in which, in addition to installing the GSHP heating system, external walls were insulated.

Figure 4: GHG emissions of each system component in the LC construction stage

The hot spots analysis of each system component, presented in Figure 4, confirms this hypothesis, that this visible difference is mainly due to the high GHG emissions of GEOFIT system components, such as: external thermal insulation for the production of which insulating materials: EPS foam board (4 kg CO₂ eq / kg) and Rockwool (1.3 kg CO₂ eq / kg) were used. A large

amount of the mortar was used for the underfloor installation, which is not always needed in this type of underfloor heating system. However, over the long-term analysis, it is significant only in the first year of system implantation, the relatively long lifespan of its components it will give a visible margin of reduction of CO₂ emissions because the energy it generates is cleaner and causes significantly lower by about 6517 kg CO₂ eq. per year (53%) compared to a traditional diesel boiler system (Figure 3). This means that the new system, after 15 years of operation, is able to reduce by around 96 t GHG emission.

The comparison of the entire heating demand and heat generation of both systems in the building before and after retrofitting is summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: GHG emissions from the consumption and generated heat energy

System	Energy heat consumption (kg CO ₂ eq / year)	Energy heat generation (kg CO ₂ eq / kWh)
Before GEOFIT	12,371.32	0.504
After GEOFIT	5,853.78	0.150

As can be seen, for the new GSHP system, the GHG emissions from the energy consumption needed to heat the entire Aran building are more than twice lower, and for the generation of 1 kWh, more than three times. For detailed illustration, Figure 5 presents the dominance analysis of GHG emissions, expressed in kg CO₂ eq. from various energy sources for the generation of 1 kWh of thermal energy by the heating systems before and after GEOFIT.

Figure 5: Environmental hot spots of 1 kWh thermal energy generated by reference and GEOFIT system

Figure above shows that 1 kWh of energy generated by the reference system is responsible for 22% of GHG emissions from diesel fuel and 78% from fossil (coal) energy. In the case of GEOFIT, the share of CO₂ emissions generated by 1 kWh comes from diesel in 26% and 74% from geothermal energy. However, for this system, more than 86% of the generated energy comes from geothermal sources and is higher than energy generated by reference system, which proves that the new system would be more beneficial and environmentally friendly than the baseline one.

REFERENCES

- Benjamin Greening, Adisa Azapagic, Domestic heat pumps: Life cycle environmental impacts and potential, *Energy* 39 (2012) 205-217
- EN 15804:2012, Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products
- EPA, Construction & Demolition Waste Statistics for Ireland, 2021, Available: <https://www.epa.ie/our-services/monitoring--assessment/waste/national-waste-statistics/construction--demolition> [Accessed 28-March-2022]
- European Commission: In focus: Energy efficiency in buildings; 17 February 2020, Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/focus-energy-efficiency-buildings-2020-lut-17_en
- European Commission JRC-IES; International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) Handbook - General guide for Life Cycle Assessment - Detailed guidance. First edition March 2010
- European Green Deal Deal, Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/delivering-european-green-deal_en#renovating-buildings-for-greener-lifestyles [Accessed 22-March-2022]
- IEA, Methodology Guidelines on Life Cycle Assessment of Photovoltaic Electricity, 2016, Available: https://iea-pvps.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Task_12_-_Methodology_Guidelines_on_Life_Cycle_Asses

The GHG emission for the GEOFIT geothermal heating system is 0.150 kgCO₂ / kWh, so it is within the range indicated in the literature.

Regarding the maintenance (replacement of materials) and EoL stages, they have little significant effect on entire GHG emissions, Figure 3.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The LCA study was carried out of a geothermal system for heating installed in the residential building on the Aran Islands (Ireland) and developed under GEOFIT project and traditional heating system before retrofitting. GEOFIT system could eliminate the use of coal and rely solely on nearly half of the less than the reference amount of diesel and small amounts of electricity.

The results of this publication have shown that the new hybrid heating geothermal system is a better alternative to reducing GHG emissions than the conventional one, mainly in terms of the heating energy used. The new system can reduce annual emissions from the operational phase by more than 53% in comparison to the reference one.

ment_of_Photovoltaic_Electricity_3rd_Edition.pdf

- International EPD® System Product Group Classification: Un Cpc 171 and 173 Electricity, Steam and Hot/Cold Water Generation and Distribution, (2007:08), version 4.2 (VALID UNTIL: 2024-03-16).
- ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework.
- ISO 14044:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines.
- IPCC-Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2013). Revised supplementary methods and good practice guidance arising from the kyoto protocol, Available: https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/kpsg/pdf/KP_Supplement_Entire_Report.pdf [Accessed: 23-March-2022]
- IEA, World Energy Outlook 2021, Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2021>
- Ireland 2050. Understanding our energy choices, Available: <http://ireland2050.ie/past/heat/> [Accessed: 28-March-2022]
- Marcella Ruschi Mendes Saade, Geoffrey Guest, Ben Amor, Comparative whole building LCAs: How far are our expectations from the documented evidence?, Building and Environment, 2019
- Maria Laura Parisi, Mélanie Douziech, Lorenzo Tosti, Paula Perez-Lopez, Barbara Mendeka, et al, Definition of LCA Guidelines in the Geothermal

Sector to Enhance Result Comparability. *Energies*, MDPI, (2020), 13 (14), 3534.

Met Éireann, The Irish Meteorological Service. Display and Download Historical Data from current stations, Available: <https://www.met.ie/climate/available-data/historical-data>. [Accessed: 21-March-2022].

SEAL, Comprehensive Assessment of the Potential for Efficient Heating and Cooling in Ireland Report to the European Commission, 2021

UNEP, Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction, 2019 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction, 2019

UNEP, Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction, 2021 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction, 2021

Viegand Maagøe and Danish Technical Institute, 2019, Review study on Local Space Heaters, Available: https://www.applia-europe.eu/images/Library/Preparatory_study_for_local_space_heaters_-_2019.pdf [Accessed: 29-March-2022].

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